

HARMLESS workshop on Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) for SMEs: Advanced Materials in Product Development

AGENDA

25th May 2023, 10:00 - 11:30 CEST, online

10:00 - 10:05	Agenda and Objectives of the Workshop by Otmar Schmid (HMGU)
10:05 - 10:20	Easy steps towards SSbD - Guidance for avoiding "obvious" risks with materials by Michael Persson (CIT)
10:20 - 10:35	Overview of HARMLESS SSbD framework and Decision Support System by Blanca Suarez (TEMASOL) and Susan Dekkers (TNO)
10:35 - 10:50	AI-based data acquisition tool & integration into existing databases by Nina Jeliaskova (IDEA)
10:50 - 11:00	Wrap up & Q&A Session Moderated by Otmar Schmid (HMGU)
11:00 - 11:30	Q&A session for SMEs who want to become involved in the project Moderated by Michael Persson (CIT)

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